

1 **Mitigation of mineral scaling in membrane capacitive deionization – understanding the**
2 **role of pH changes and carbonates**

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15

16 **Highlights**

- 17
- 18 • pH changes during tap water desalination using membrane capacitive deionization are
19 a result of the adsorption and desorption of HCO_3^- ions and associated changes in the
20 dissolved inorganic carbon (DIC) concentration.
 - 21 • pH changes lead to mineral scaling, especially at higher water recovery (WR) conditions
(i.e., $\text{WR} > 50\%$).

- 1 • Increasing the thickness of the anion exchange membrane (AEM) reduces mineral
2 scaling.

3

4 **Abstract**

5 Mineral scaling in water desalination is caused by the precipitation of salts, which is affected
6 by various factors such as the presence of specific ions, solution pH, and temperature. While
7 extensively researched in technologies like reverse osmosis (RO), understanding mineral
8 scaling in membrane capacitive deionization (MCDI) remains limited. During MCDI operation,
9 the pH of the effluent fluctuates, potentially triggering mineral scaling. The present study
10 investigates how the adsorption and desorption of HCO_3^- ions and the distribution of dissolved
11 inorganic carbon (DIC) species (H_2CO_3 , HCO_3^- , and CO_3^{2-}) drive pH changes. We examine
12 mineral scaling formation at various water recoveries during MCDI operation using different
13 thicknesses of the anion exchange membrane (AEM). Our findings indicate that pH changes
14 increase with higher water recoveries and that increasing the AEM thickness provides a
15 pathway to enhance MCDI stability, consequently lowering the need for anti-scaling agents.

16 **Keywords:** membrane capacitive deionization, pH changes, dissolved inorganic carbon,
17 mineral scaling, ion-exchange membrane.

18 1. Introduction

19 Desalination technologies play a vital role in addressing water scarcity issues by producing
20 fresh water, particularly in regions with limited access to natural freshwater sources.[1–3]

21 Desalination processes remove salt ions from the source water employing various driving forces
22 such as temperature, pressure, or electrical potential differences.[4–9]. For instance, in thermal
23 desalination methods like multi-effect distillation (MED), the feed water undergoes

1 vaporization, and upon condensation, purified water is obtained, while the salt is left behind in
 2 the concentrate [7,10] Reverse osmosis (RO) and nanofiltration (NF) techniques involve the
 3 passage of water through semi-permeable membranes under pressure, separating desalinated
 4 water from a concentrated stream rich in salt ions.[4,11–15] In membrane capacitive
 5 deionization (MCDI) and electro dialysis (ED), an electrical potential difference is applied to
 6 extract salt ions from saline water, generating desalinated water and concentrate.[8,9,16]
 7 Despite their differences, all these technologies share a common challenge: the concentration
 8 of ions in the concentrate is higher than in the feed water, posing a potential risk of mineral
 9 scaling.

10 In the context of MCDI, various factors influence mineral scaling, including salt solubility
 11 limits, ion types, and solution pH.[5,10,17,18] Particularly noteworthy is the impact of hardness
 12 ions such as Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} , as they tend to precipitate as carbonate, sulfate, or phosphate salts,
 13 resulting in mineral scaling in MCDI systems. Mineral scaling in MCDI can impact long-term
 14 salt removal efficiency and energy consumption, leading to increased operational costs and
 15 greater reliance on anti-scaling agents.[8,11,12,19,20] Despite numerous strategies proposed to
 16 mitigate scaling in conventional desalination methods such as RO and MED, understanding and
 17 controlling scaling in MCDI remain limited.[13,17]

Figure 1. (a) MCDI operation during the charging step and (b) the effluent pH during the desalination of a NaHCO_3 solution, (c) the impact of pH changes in CDI and MCDI.

1 An MCDI cell consists of two porous carbon electrodes (an anode and a cathode), two ion-
2 exchange membranes (IEMs) (an anion exchange membrane (AEM) positioned in front of the
3 anode and a cation exchange membrane (CEM) in front of the cathode), and a porous spacer
4 material used to separate the electrodes and facilitate water flow during operation. The MCDI
5 cell is alternatingly charged to adsorb ions, resulting in the production of desalinated water, and
6 discharged to desorb ions, resulting in the production of a concentrate solution (Figure 1a).
7 Throughout MCDI's cyclic operation, noticeable pH fluctuations are observed in the effluent,
8 as shown in Figure 1b. Notably, the discharge phase yields a higher pH than the feedwater. This
9 pH elevation during discharge triggers mineral scaling, underscoring the importance of
10 understanding the underlying mechanisms behind these pH changes. Such insights are essential
11 for improving the long-term stability of MCDI systems.

12 Earlier studies of pH fluctuations in MCDI systems postulated that such changes originated
13 from faradaic processes like water splitting, carbon oxidation, and the generation of Cl_2 gas.
14 However, there are also studies indicating theoretically and experimentally that non-faradaic
15 processes, such as water dissociation because of disparities in ion transport rates, can also
16 contribute to pH alterations.[21–24] As MCDI cells undergo numerous desalination cycles, the
17 electrodes gradually age, diminishing the significance of faradaic reactions like carbon
18 oxidation due to the depletion of available carbon groups for oxidation. Consequently, non-
19 faradaic processes emerge as the primary cause of pH changes. [25]

20 In our previous work using aged electrodes, we have shown that pH fluctuations in brackish
21 water desalination stem from the adsorption and desorption of bicarbonate ions (HCO_3^-).
22 During charging, HCO_3^- ions are adsorbed, resulting in a decrease in effluent pH. Conversely,
23 discharge results in the desorption of HCO_3^- ions, leading to a rise in effluent pH. When the
24 concentrations of ions such as Ca^{2+} and HCO_3^- increase, mineral scaling may also exacerbate
25 as these ions can precipitate as CaCO_3 salt.[25]

1 Previous studies on mineral scaling in MCDI have clarified that scaling primarily occurs on the
2 membranes and the spacer channel, with minimal impact on the electrode surfaces compared to
3 CDI, where scaling occurs in spacers and electrodes as depicted in figure 1c. This is attributed
4 to the IEMs effectively hindering the movement of co-ions. Specifically, the AEM serves as a
5 barrier to the transport of Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} ions towards the anode. Meanwhile, anions (HCO_3^- ,
6 PO_4^{3-} , and SO_4^{2-}) are hindered by the CEM from transporting towards the cathode, where Ca^{2+}
7 and Mg^{2+} ions are electrosorbed.[26,27] In addition to Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} , other ions such as
8 $\text{Fe}^{2+}/\text{Fe}^{3+}$ and Ba^{2+} can also precipitate, contingent on their concentrations, the presence of
9 different counterions, and the pH of the feed water. Wang et al. examined Fe^{2+} scaling in MCDI,
10 observing Fe^{2+} precipitation on both the AEM, CEM, and the spacer.[27] Despite this
11 advancement, a comprehensive understanding of how changes in pH affect mineral scaling
12 remains an unresolved aspect.

13 To address the challenges associated with mineral scaling in MCDI, this study systematically
14 conducts desalination experiments using tap water and synthetic water. Effluent pH changes
15 are recorded at various water recovery (WR) levels. These pH changes are elucidated by the
16 removal of HCO_3^- ions and subsequent changes in the distribution of dissolved inorganic carbon
17 (DIC) species. Furthermore, a mitigation strategy is devised to mitigate mineral scaling by
18 adjusting the thickness of the AEM.

19 2. Materials and methods

20 2.1. MCDI stack construction

21 The MCDI stack consisted of three cells, each comprising two graphitic current collectors, two
22 activated carbon electrodes (PACMM 203, $\delta_e \sim 250 \mu\text{m}$, Material Methods, Irvine, CA, USA),
23 a cation exchange membrane (CEM), an anion exchange membrane (AEM), and a porous
24 spacer. The CEM (140 μm thick, Neosepta CMX, ASTOM Corporation, Tokyo, Japan) was

1 positioned in front of the cathode, while the AEM (140 μm thick, Neosepta AMX, ASTOM
2 Corporation, Tokyo, Japan) was in front of the anode. A nylon spacer (160 μm thick) was placed
3 between the membranes. The graphite current collectors were situated behind each activated
4 carbon electrode. To augment the thickness of the AEM within the stack, an extra AEM was
5 placed in each cell.

6 2.2. Desalination experiments

7 Desalination experiments used three types of feed water: tap water (sourced from Wetsus,
8 Leeuwarden, The Netherlands), synthetic water (prepared by dissolving NaCl, CaCl₂, NaHCO₃
9 and CaCO₃ salts in deionized water), and a NaHCO₃ salt solution (prepared by dissolving
10 NaHCO₃ salt in deionized water). Detailed ionic compositions are provided in Table S1. Water
11 was circulated through the stack at a rate of 17 ml/min, achieving a productivity (P) of 55 L/h/m²
12 at 50% WR. To increase water recovery, the flow rate during discharge was reduced.
13 Experiments were conducted in constant current (CC) mode using an Ivium-n-stat potentiostat
14 (Ivium technologies, The Netherlands) with a current density of 11.1 A/m² during charging and
15 reversed current during discharging. The half cycle time was 160 seconds, except for
16 asymmetric experiments (See section 2.2.3). Desalination experiments were performed at
17 various water recovery conditions (WR, the ratio of desalinated water over the total volume of
18 water treated) in single-pass mode (i.e., effluent water was drained). The pressure difference
19 (Δp) between the stack inlet and outlet was continuously monitored using a differential pressure
20 meter (EJA110E, Yokogawa Electric Corporation, Japan). Effluent pH and conductivity were
21 also continuously recorded with 2-second data intervals using pH and conductivity sensors.

22 2.2.1. Feed water pH adjustment

23 In experiments involving tap water, the feed pH was measured at 7.73 ± 0.05 . However, in the
24 case of the NaHCO₃ solution and synthetic tap water, the initial feed pH was higher than that

1 of tap water and exhibited variability over time due to interactions with atmospheric CO₂. To
2 ensure a consistent comparison of pH changes during MCDI operation across different feed
3 water compositions, we purged the NaHCO₃ solution and synthetic water with CO₂ to establish
4 and maintain a stable feedwater pH of 7.73. Once pH=7.73 was attained, it remained relatively
5 stable (7.73 ± 0.03) throughout the experimental duration.

6 2.2.2. Sample collection and ionic composition analysis

7 In addition to continuous pH monitoring, we employed two methods for collecting desalinated
8 water and concentrate samples. The first method involved sample collection throughout the
9 entire charging or discharging step (i.e., 160 seconds), while the second method focused
10 specifically on samples collected during the final 50 seconds of the charging or discharging
11 step, representing the steady-state period. Following sample collection, we measured the pH
12 and conductivity of each sample (within approximately 5 minutes). For the determination of
13 cationic and anionic concentrations, we used inductively coupled plasma-optical emission
14 spectroscopy (ICP-OES, Optima 5300 DV, PerkinElmer) and ion chromatography (IC, Dionex
15 Aquion, Thermo Scientific), respectively. The bicarbonate ion concentration was calculated
16 using Aqion software, employing charge and mass balance calculations involving all other
17 measured ions.

18 2.2.3. Asymmetric desalination experiments

19 Experiments involving asymmetric desalination conditions, where variations occur between the
20 charging and discharging steps, are conducted. In each experiment, parameters during the
21 charging step, such as flow rate (17 ml/min for the stack), charging time (160 seconds), and
22 current density (11.1 A/m² for the stack), remained constant. However, during the discharging
23 step, only the flow rate remained constant, while the discharging time and current density were
24 adjusted to ensure that the total charge transferred during the discharging step matched that of

1 the charging step. Specific discharge conditions employed in asymmetric experiments are
2 outlined in detail in Table S2.

3 2.3. Mineral scaling experiments

4 Mineral scaling experiments were conducted using two configurations of the MCDI stack: one
5 with a single AEM (Single-AEM MCDI) and the other with double AEM (Double-AEM
6 MCDI), as described in section 2.1. For tap water, scaling experiments were conducted
7 continuously for over 100 hours of operation, while for synthetic water, they were carried out
8 for a duration of 17.8 hours (200 cycles). Throughout the scaling experiments, continuous
9 measurement of the pressure difference (Δp) across the MCDI stack inlet and outlet was
10 performed. Following each experiment, the stack underwent a cleaning process involving the
11 circulation of a 0.1 M HCl solution through the stack until Δp returned to its initial value (+/-
12 10 mbar). This cleaning procedure, typically lasting 2-4 hours, aimed to remove any scale
13 formation and prepare the cell for subsequent experiments. After acid cleaning, the feed water
14 was pumped through the cell until both the feed pH and effluent pH were equal.

15 2.4. Calculation of ionic composition, saturation index, DIC, and titration.

16 Aqion Pro 8.1.5 software was used to compute the concentrations of the DIC species (H_2CO_3 ,
17 HCO_3^- , and CO_3^{2-}), as well as the Langelier saturation index (LSI) in both the feed water and
18 the samples collected during charging and discharging. Additionally, titration curves for
19 NaHCO_3 titration with an acid were generated using the software. These calculations were
20 performed by taking into account charge and mass balance principles. The calculations were
21 conducted within a closed CO_2 system, meaning there was no interaction with the atmosphere.

22 2.4.1. Ionic composition calculations for feed water

1 In the feed water, all ions except for carbonates are experimentally measured, along with pH.
2 These measured concentrations and pH values are then input into the software to calculate the
3 DIC concentration, including HCO_3^- and CO_3^{2-} . The calculations were performed using the
4 software, employing charge and mass balance principles, while assuming a closed CO_2 system.

5 2.4.2. Ionic composition & LSI calculations for collected samples

6 In analysing the ionic composition of collected samples, we used both the measured ionic
7 concentrations and pH as fixed parameters to compute the concentrations of dissolved inorganic
8 carbon (DIC). The pH measured experimentally in these collected samples represents the
9 average pH of the total volume of desalinated or concentrate water collected during the entire
10 step. Hence, the calculated DIC concentrations reflect the concentrations for the entire
11 adsorption or desorption cycle, based on the measured pH. To account for varying pH values
12 and their impact on ionic composition, different pH inputs were used, and a charge balance was
13 conducted for each pH value to ascertain the corresponding ionic composition, including DIC
14 concentrations. Additionally, these calculations facilitated the extraction of the Langelier
15 Saturation Index (LSI) values for each sample from the software. The detailed calculation
16 method of LSI is outlined in our previous study.[25]

17 2.4.3. DIC calculation for NaHCO_3 desalination

18 The DIC concentration during NaHCO_3 desalination was calculated by using the effluent Na^+
19 concentration (calculated from effluent conductivity) and the effluent pH as inputs. With these
20 inputs, the DIC concentration is calculated through charge and mass balances considering a
21 closed system.

22 2.4.4. Titration calculations

1 To predict the titration curves in Aqion Pro, we input the concentrations of NaHCO_3 , and the
2 charge balance is adjusted based on the DIC concentration before titrating against HCl (50
3 mM). The titration predictions take into account a closed CO_2 system, mirroring the conditions
4 of the experimental titrations conducted in a closed vessel.

5 3. Results and discussion

6 **3.1. pH changes in MCDI**

7 We conducted desalination experiments using tap water, a synthetic solution containing a
8 limited set of salts (consisting of Na^+ , Ca^{2+} , Cl^- , and HCO_3^-), and a single salt solution (only
9 Na^+ and HCO_3^-) to elucidate the underlying mechanisms for pH changes. As depicted in Figure
10 2(a-c), the charging step induces a decrease in pH, while discharging leads to an increase in pH
11 across all feed waters. Notably, the effluent pH changes demonstrate consistent trends in terms
12 of both direction and dynamics for both the NaHCO_3 (single salt) solution and multi-ionic salt
13 solutions (tap water, multi-ionic synthetic water). However, in previous work we have
14 demonstrated that for single salt solutions, when the anion present is Cl^- instead of HCO_3^- , the
15 resulting pH changes differ in terms of direction and dynamics, as demonstrated by the
16 desalination of NaCl solution instead of NaHCO_3 , as shown in Figure 2d.

17 This finding suggests that the presence of different anions in the water impacts the changes in
18 effluent pH. The diverging trends in pH may stem from variations in anion compositions;
19 specifically, the amphoteric nature of HCO_3^- allows it to function as both an acid and a base,
20 influencing pH, whereas Cl^- does not buffer the solution pH. Previous research by Arulrajan et
21 al.[25] has shown that, under identical experimental conditions (11.1 A/m^2 current density, feed
22 water equilibrated with the atmosphere, and voltages below 0.95 V), faradaic reactions occur
23 solely at pristine electrodes, and as electrodes age, pH changes are predominantly attributed to
24 non-faradaic processes.[25] Hence, faradaic reactions can be discounted as a potential cause of

1 pH changes, with focus instead on HCO_3^- ion adsorption and desorption as the primary driver
 2 in feed waters where these ions are present.
 3 To investigate the impact of effluent concentration on pH changes, we conducted additional
 4 desalination experiments using freshly prepared NaHCO_3 with an initial feed pH of 8.35. By
 5 adjusting the applied current density to the MCDI stack, we adjusted the ion concentration in
 6 the effluent water (Δc). Figure 3a presents the mean effluent pH during adsorption and
 7 desorption steps relative to the applied current density. As the charging current density increases
 8 from 4.95 A/m^2 to 8.9 A/m^2 , the effluent pH decreases from 8.31 to 8.26. Conversely, during
 9 discharge, the effluent pH rises from 8.41 to 8.46. This observation indicates that modifying

Figure 2. Effluent pH changes observed during desalination of a) tap water, b) synthetic water, c) a NaHCO_3 solution and d) an NaCl solution (adapted from our previous study, Arulrajan et al. (2021)). The feed pH of the NaCl solution is 7, while for all other feed waters the pH is 7.72.

1 the applied current density to alter ion concentrations in the effluent directly influences the
2 magnitude of pH variations in tap water.

Figure 3. (a) Averaged effluent pH of the experiment with the NaHCO_3 solution during charging and discharging, (b) the effluent pH changes during asymmetric desalination experiments, and (c) the magnitude of pH spikes at the beginning of the charging step.

3 To understand the effect of operational parameters such as current density, which can affect the
4 effluent concentration and subsequently pH changes, particularly for concentrates, we
5 conducted asymmetric desalination experiments using tap water. Throughout these
6 experiments, the conditions (i.e., flow rate, current density, and charging time) during the
7 charging step remained the same across all experiments, but the conditions during the
8 discharging step were varied (maintaining a constant flow rate while altering the current density
9 and discharging times). In these asymmetric experiments, the change in effluent concentration
10 during charging remained consistent across all cycles due to the uniformity of experimental
11 conditions, whereas the effluent concentration during discharging is affected by the applied
12 current. The cell voltage during asymmetric experiments is presented in Figure S1. When the
13 current was increased during discharging, the discharging time was proportionally reduced to
14 keep the total charge transferred during discharge the same for all applied currents. Figure 3b
15 shows the effluent pH during asymmetric desalination. The pH changes observed in different
16 asymmetric experiments overlapped during the charging step, while during the discharging
17 step, the magnitude of effluent pH changes increases with increasing current density. A

1 noteworthy aspect of pH changes is the distinct pH spike at the beginning of the charging step,
2 followed by a smaller yet inverted pH spike at the beginning of the discharging step, as shown
3 in Figure 2a-c. As illustrated in Figure 3b, the magnitude of the pH spike during the charging
4 step was influenced by the current density applied during charging, with higher current densities
5 resulting in larger pH spikes. These pH spikes can induce mineral scaling, particularly when
6 hardness ions are present at elevated concentrations.

7 **3.2. pH changes with high DIC concentrations**

8 To investigate the mechanisms causing pH changes, we focussed on a simpler solution than tap
9 water, i.e., a NaHCO₃ solution. Despite the effluent pH fluctuations during charging and
10 discharging, the effluent concentration stabilizes at a steady plateau value shortly after the start
11 of a charging or discharging step (Figure 4a), characteristic of constant current operation. The
12 HCO₃⁻ ions, being amphoteric, participate in the carbonic acid equilibrium expressed as: H₂O
13 + CO₂(g) ⇌ H₂CO₃^{*} ⇌ HCO₃⁻ + H⁺ ⇌ CO₃²⁻ + 2H⁺ (Apparent H₂CO₃^{*} represents the combined
14 concentrations of H₂CO₃ and aqueous CO₂). This equilibrium governs the concentration of each
15 species involved, including CO₂(g), DIC (H₂CO₃^{*}, HCO₃⁻, and CO₃²⁻), along with pH.[28]
16 Throughout charging and discharging, the adsorption and desorption of charged DIC species
17 affect the carbonic acid equilibrium, leading to a shift in pH.[25]

18 We used Aqion Pro software to compute the DIC concentration from the effluent pH and Na⁺
19 concentration, employing the methodology outlined in the materials and methods section. This
20 analysis aims to elucidate changes in DIC species (CO₂, H₂CO₃, HCO₃⁻, and CO₃²⁻)
21 concentrations. Notably, we calculated the concentrations of apparent H₂CO₃^{*}, HCO₃⁻, and
22 CO₃²⁻ while treating the MCDI stack as a closed system (i.e., no CO₂ exchange with
23 atmospheric air). In the pH range between 7 and 8, H₂CO₃^{*} and HCO₃⁻ emerge as the dominant
24 DIC species, while the concentration of CO₃²⁻ is negligible, as shown in Figure S2 and S3.

Figure 4. (a) The effluent NaHCO₃ concentration and pH during charging and discharging of MCDI. (b) The calculated concentrations of two primary DIC species, namely HCO₃⁻ and H₂CO₃^{*}, during charging and discharging.

1 Figure 4a displays the effluent pH and the NaHCO₃ concentration, while Figure 4b shows the
 2 concentrations of H₂CO₃^{*} and HCO₃⁻ over time. Clearly, due to the adsorption and desorption
 3 of charged DIC in the porous carbon electrodes, the equilibrium between H₂CO₃^{*} and HCO₃⁻
 4 is shifted. This shift in chemical equilibrium impacts the solution pH, as shown in Figure 4a.
 5 Specifically, during charging, the H₂CO₃^{*} concentration experiences a sharp initial decline
 6 from the feed concentration (~200 μM to ~60 μM), followed by gradual increase, ultimately
 7 returning to the initial feed water concentration (200 μM) by the end of the charging step.
 8 Similarly, during discharge, the H₂CO₃^{*} concentration undergoes a sharp increase (from ~200
 9 μM to ~1 mM), followed by a gradual decline, once again reaching the initial feed concentration
 10 (200 μM) by the end of the discharging step. The sharp changes in H₂CO₃^{*} concentration
 11 coincide with the pH spike at the onset of the charging step, while the sharp decrease aligns
 12 with the inverted pH spike at the beginning of the discharging step.

13 Figure 4b shows that the rapid H₂CO₃^{*} concentration change at the beginning of discharging
 14 (~0.75 mM) is approximately sixfold higher than the corresponding change during charging
 15 (~0.13 mM). However, this notable concentration increase does not translate into a
 16 proportionately amplified pH spike during discharge. As NaHCO₃ solution is a buffered

1 solution, it is important to consider the buffer range of this solution to evaluate the reason for
2 the magnitude in pH changes. At the beginning of the discharging step, the effluent pH is 7.1,
3 which is close to the pK_a (6.37) of the carbonic acid-bicarbonate equilibrium,[29] indicating
4 that the pH is minimally impacted by changes in the concentration of DIC species.. At the
5 beginning of the charging step, however, the effluent pH is 7.9, which is further away from the
6 pK_a of 6.37, and is therefore in the poorly buffered pH range. This lower buffer capacity could
7 be the reason for the more pronounced pH spike at the beginning of the charging step. This
8 argument is supported by the calculation conducted for the titration of $NaHCO_3$ composition
9 measured during discharge, see Figure S7.

10 **3.3. Mineral scaling in MCDI**

11 The pH changes in MCDI can induce scaling, especially noticeable under high water recovery
12 conditions ($WR > 50\%$).[30] During the investigation of mineral scaling, we examined various
13 water recovery conditions. Our focus was on assessing the impact of AEM thickness on mineral
14 scaling, as membrane thickness can influence the flux ratio of different species.[31] Two
15 configurations of MCDI stacks were employed: one with a single-AEM MCDI cell and the
16 other with a double-AEM MCDI cell setup. Desalination experiments were conducted for
17 durations exceeding 100 hours for each water recovery condition. To enhance water recovery,
18 the flow rate during discharge was reduced. Mineral scaling in the flow channel was monitored
19 by continuously measuring the pressure difference (Δp) across the spacer channel during
20 experiments.[30]

1 The Δp measured between the inlet and outlet of the MCDI cell represents the pressure
2 difference across the spacer channel connecting the inlet and outlet. Mineral scaling occurs
3 when minerals precipitate, blocking pores in the spacer. This blockage leads to an increase in
4 Δp . In MCDI systems, Δp values often serve as indicators prompting cleaning cycles for mineral
5 scale removal. Typically, cleaning cycles commence just before Δp begins to rise exponentially;
6 however, specifics vary between systems, lacking a standardized protocol for cleaning cycle
7 initiation. In this study, a threshold of 100 mbar was set to compare mineral scaling across
8 operational conditions.

Figure 5. Pressure difference, an indication for mineral scaling, across the MCDI cell against operational time during tap water desalination at water recoveries a) 50%, b) 75%, c) 85%, d) 90%.

1 Figure 5 shows that, for tap water desalination, an increase in Δp with time is observed, which
2 is an indicator of mineral scaling. Notably, at 50% and 75% WR conditions, Δp remains
3 relatively stable, with values below 20 mbar even after 110 hours of operation. At 85% WR,
4 although scaling causes a more pronounced increase in Δp , it does not reach the threshold of
5 100 mbar during the experiment. Only at WR of 90%, substantial Δp changes occur over time
6 in both MCDI configurations. For the single-AEM MCDI, 100 mbar is reached in 35 hours;
7 whereas, with double-AEM MCDI, it takes ~80 hours. This observation gives experimental
8 support that increasing AEM thickness reduces mineral scaling, and therefore the consumption
9 of cleaning in place chemicals.

10 Experiments with tap water were poorly reproducible. Subsequent examination upon MCDI
11 stack disassembly revealed pronounced mineral scaling exclusively on the spacer as visibly
12 depicted in Figure S4, whereas IEMs remained largely unaffected. The precipitated salt in the
13 spacer was subjected to Raman spectral analysis. The Raman analysis shows 4 distinctive peaks
14 at 153, 280, 712 and 1085 cm^{-1} which are in line with the peaks for calcite (CaCO_3) revealing
15 that the precipitated mineral is calcite, see Figure S5.[32] Interestingly, the initially transparent
16 AEMs exhibited a brown hue (as seen in Figure S6), potentially attributable to organic
17 adsorption (e.g., humic/fluvic acid substances). This membrane fouling could impair
18 experimental reproducibility. Therefore, we studied scaling in synthetic water containing only
19 Na^+ and Ca^{2+} cations, and Cl^- and $\text{HCO}_3^-/\text{CO}_3^{2-}$ anions, with increased Ca^{2+} ion concentrations
20 to accelerate mineral scaling (Table S1). These synthetic water scaling experiments were
21 carried out for 200 desalination cycles (equivalent to ~18 hours), repeated three times for 85%
22 and 90% WR to ensure replicability.

23 Figure 6 shows Δp changes over operational time for synthetic water. Similar to the trends
24 observed in tap water mineral scaling, experiments with synthetic water also demonstrate an
25 increase in scaling with rising WR. However, at 50% and 75% WR, though Δp increases it does

1 not reach the 100 mbar threshold within the ~18-hour operational timeframe. At 85% WR, the
2 single-AEM MCDI stack reaches 100 mbar Δp in 14 hours, while the double-AEM MCDI stack
3 does not reach the 100 mbar threshold within the operational timeframe. Upon increasing the
4 WR to 90%, the single-AEM MCDI achieves a 100 mbar Δp in 10 hours, whereas the double-
5 AEM MCDI stack takes 13.5 hours, displaying that scaling is approximately 1.35 times slower.
6 In experiments with tap water and synthetic water, mineral scaling is primarily influenced by
7 two factors: the hardness ion concentration (Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+}) and pH. Analysis of ionic composition
8 in tap water experiments shows no significant difference between single AEM and double AEM
9 configurations. Effluent pH data from tap water and synthetic water experiments alone cannot
10 explain pH variations by the AEM thickness, as simultaneous scaling can impact the measured
11 effluent pH. To address this, we conducted theoretical calculations of the Langelier Saturation
12 Index (LSI). The LSI is an indicator that shows the extent of scaling potential of a solution
13 based on pH, TDS (total dissolved solids), temperature, Ca^{2+} concentration and alkalinity.
14 While desalinating tap water or artificial tap water, at higher WR, the concentration of Ca^{2+}
15 ions (together with all other ions) and pH in the effluent increases. This results in the
16 precipitation of CaCO_3 (calcite) on the spacer. When the LSI values are above 0.5, the potential
17 for scaling is significantly high. We calculated the LSI for the concentrate composition of 90%
18 water recovery under two conditions: firstly, varying the Ca^{2+} concentration (and Na^+
19 concentration to maintain the charge balance) with constant pH, and secondly, varying pH and
20 the total DIC concentration while the other ionic concentrations are constant, see Figure S8.
21 The initial LSI value for the concentrate is 1, and to raise the LSI to 1.2, the Ca^{2+} concentration
22 must increase by 73% (i.e., from 3.42 mM to 5.92 mM) when pH is fixed, while a 2.9% increase
23 in pH (i.e., from 8.02 to 8.25) results in the same LSI with fixed concentrations of Ca^{2+} and of
24 the other ions except DIC. As the difference in the Ca^{2+} concentration between single AEM and
25 CEM experiments is not significant (i.e., only 8.75%), the difference in effluent pH between

1 single and double AEM is probably the most important cause of the observed differences in
2 scaling, as shown in Figure 5 and 6.

Figure 6. Pressure difference across the MCDI cell against operational time as an indication for mineral scaling during synthetic water desalination at water recoveries a) 50%, b) 75%, c) 85%, d) 90%. The dotted and solid lines of the same colour show data from replicate experiments.

3 4. Conclusion

4 We conducted a series of experiments to understand the mechanisms driving pH changes during
5 desalination processes, focusing on solutions containing HCO_3^- ions (such as tap water,
6 synthetic water and NaHCO_3). Our empirical findings demonstrate that pH changes observed
7 in NaHCO_3 experiments directly result from HCO_3^- removal, which we identify as a significant
8 mechanism driving pH changes in tap water. Through systematic experiments and calculations,
9 we determined that HCO_3^- removal, along with changes in concentrations of other dissolved

1 inorganic carbon (DIC) species, can lead to pH changes by altering the carbonic acid
2 equilibrium. Furthermore, we observed that desalination of tap water or synthetic water
3 containing hardness ions at higher WR conditions results in elevated pH levels, contributing to
4 increased mineral scaling. Raman spectral analysis revealed that during tap water desalination,
5 scaling primarily occurs due to the precipitation of calcite mineral. Our findings also
6 demonstrate that increasing the thickness of the AEM can reduce mineral scaling in MCDI,
7 consequently decreasing the need for anti-scaling agents.

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19 **Declaration of competing interest**

20 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal
21 relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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1 Graphical abstract

pH changes in MCDI

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1 **Supporting information**

2 **Mitigation of mineral scaling in membrane capacitive deionization – understanding the**
3 **role of pH changes and carbonates**

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16

1 Table S1. Composition of different feed water solutions at pH 7.73 with experimentally
 2 measured ionic compositions. The concentrations of HCO_3^- and CO_3^{2-} are calculated using
 3 Aqion Pro software as mentioned in the method section.

Ion	Concentration (mM)		
	Tap water (pH 7.72)	Synthetic water (pH 7.73)	NaHCO_3 water (pH 7.73)
Cations			
Na^+	3.08	1.97	4.93
Ca^{2+}	0.79	1.92	-
K^+	0.08	-	-
Mg^{2+}	0.40	-	-
Anions			
HCO_3^-	4.43 (calculated)	4.63 (calculated)	4.89 (calculated)
CO_3^{2-}	0.014 (calculated)	0.015 (calculated)	0.015 (calculated)
Cl^-	1.05	1.02	-
NO_3^{2-}	0.06	-	-
SO_4^{2-}	< detection limit	-	-
PO_4^{3-}	< detection limit	-	-

4
 5 Table S2. Current and discharging time during the discharging step in asymmetric desalination
 6 experiments.

Current (A/m^2)	Discharging time (s)	Equivalent WR %
5.93	300	27
7.41	240	33.5
9.88	180	44.5
11.11	160	50
14.81	120	67

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 8

1 Charge and Mass balance calculations

2 The charge and mass balance calculations were carried out by Aqion Pro software as mentioned
3 in the methods section. To calculate the concentration of each DIC species, the following
4 equations are used by the software.

5 For a closed DIC system,

6 Mass balance: $[\text{DIC}] = [\text{H}_2\text{CO}_3^*] + [\text{HCO}_3^-] + [\text{CO}_3^{2-}] = \text{Constant}$

7 Charge balance: $[\text{H}^+] - [\text{HCO}_3^-] - 2 [\text{CO}_3^{2-}] - [\text{OH}^-] = 0$

8

Figure S1 The cell voltage profiles during asymmetric desalination experiments.

Figure S2. The carbonic species distribution for desalinated water and for concentrate with pH calculated using Aqion Pro software.

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Figure S3. The carbonate concentration and the effluent pH changes during a complete desalination cycle.

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Figure S4. Unused and used spacer in tap water experiments; mineral scaling is observed on the used spacer.

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Figure S5. Raman spectra of precipitated salt collected from MCDI spacer

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Figure S6. (a) A picture of a pristine AEM and (b) an used AEM in tap water experiments; the colour change is clearly visible.

Figure S7. Predicted titration curve for the concentrate in NaHCO_3 desalination at 50% WR condition. The green highlighted area shows the buffer range with limited pH changes when HCl is dosed.

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Figure S8. LSI prediction for concentrate composition of 90% WR tap water experiments as a function of (a) pH, and (b) of the Ca^{2+} concentration.